

USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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The integration of innovative digital technologies into the educational space is associated with a change in the methodological paradigm in the process of teaching foreign languages. The need to form an artificial language environment predetermines the use of various digital tools on the educational platform, ensuring the development of linguistic competence of students in the conditions of independent education, cognitive and motivational activity of bachelors, the creation of practice-oriented modeling of the language environment, and overcoming the linguistic barrier in the practice of foreign language communication.

Digital tools for managing the process of mastering foreign languages predetermine the development of such areas as communication, interactive interaction, authenticity of communication, visualization of learning content, and the development of language creativity. Modern multimedia technologies in the practice of teaching a foreign language provide information support and simulation of real communication, thereby facilitating the learning of fluent navigation in a foreign language environment.

Digital means of teaching a foreign language as interactive systems that integrate animated computer graphics, sound, video files, static texts and images into the educational space became the topic of research by N.A. Plastinina [4]. The author examines in detail the effectiveness of using:

- ✓ digital applications: EasyBib, Remember the Milk, SurveyMonkey, Bubbl.us, Create-a-Graph;
- ✓ electronic textbooks: Speakout, ActiveBook, MySpeakoutLab, Business Result, Market Leader, MyGrammarLab;
- ✓ electronic simulators: Letter Generator, EssayMap, LearningApps.org, TOEIC Listening - Useful English, influencing students through various information channels, developing self-organization skills.

The study of the motivational component and productive self-knowledge in the process of teaching a foreign language as one of the factors in the individualization of educational practices is reflected in the works of such scientists as A.M. Rust, L.V. Bogdanova [1].

The issues of the adequacy of the use of digital technologies in the educational process and their negative impact on students have not yet been fully developed. Thus, the problem of “information oversaturation” of education, uncontrolled and chaotic use of information is reflected in the work of I.V. Robert [2]. The author introduces the concept of content “blindness,” when the uncontrolled search for information by participants in the educational process becomes more important than completing a task using digital tools and achieving the goal. The relationship between the integration of digital tools that implement interactive dialogue among students and the weakening of social communication skills and the ability for critical, creative and problematic thinking is noted in his work by A.N. Zemskova, A.N. Kolesnichenko [3].

The use of digital technologies in a foreign language course can be implemented on various online platforms, in any form of education - full-time, part-time, independent, distance learning, for any student population. However, it is necessary to take into account the real purpose of using digital tools, the time allocated for performing exercises with digital content in the general lesson plan, the color scheme of the video resource, and a readable font to prevent student fatigue and oversaturation of the lesson with information flows.

The use of digital educational resources to improve the linguistic competence of students in the context of independent education, in our case, Internet resources that integrate audiovisual information, are considered using the example of YouTube and TED ED, which are the largest video hosting services in the world. Features of the functioning of these Internet resources are as follows:

- 1) openness, accessibility and editability of their use in the educational process;
- 2) the ability to quickly and easily create new digital objects: presentations, texts, images, video and audio files;
- 3) the existence of video materials in the original version in a foreign language;
- 4) the ability to re-watch videos and complete tasks for them online and offline. The use of video resources in the educational space allows you to divide the video material into thematic fragments in order to study in more detail the

video file seen in the lesson, which promotes the full involvement of each participant in the educational process to improve the linguistic competence of students in the conditions of independent education [2].

The effectiveness of the use of digital educational resources to improve the linguistic competence of students in the conditions of independent education in the opportunity to become familiar with the variety of accents, timbres, tempo, and dialectical features of modern authentic material. The relevance of using podcasts in the educational space is confirmed by the ease of implementation of various types of tasks aimed at developing various types of speech activity. Thus, watching video blogs, modern shows, scientific, news, and sports interviews contributes to variable learning of listening skills as a complex type of speech activity. For the development of speaking, as a complex type of speech activity, video content becomes the meaningful basis for educational discussions, round tables, and press conferences. Viewing subtitles, text accompaniment, developing and completing tasks based on subtitles contribute to the development of reading skills. The effectiveness of podcasts in the development of lexical and grammatical aspects of speech activity is confirmed by the use and development of lexical units, grammatical structures, and ranking them by topic. Thus, digital technologies help to intensify the creative activity of students, provide the opportunity to take part in thematic forums, virtual discussions, involve students in joint creative projects, create communicative situations, thereby ensuring the implementation of an individual approach and increasing motivational and cognitive activity when using digital educational resources to improve the linguistic competence of students in the conditions of independent education.

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